

Reflection exercise Modul 2, theme 2: Future Circular Collider in the Eyes of Thomas P. Hughes' Technological Systems

Future Circular Collider (FCC) is the newest design of a particle collider, which suppose to extend the current research conducted by Large Hadron Collider (LHC). FCC pushes the energy requirements for the particle collisions to 100 teraelectronvolts (TeV) and the size of 100km under Geneva, Switzerland and France. Compared to the LHC with 14TeV energy and 27km it is a very ambitious project with extensive demands on invention, development, innovation, knowledge transfer, technological style, and momentum. Not to mention 21 billion Euros to finance it (www.cern.ch).

According to Thomas P. Hughes the large technological systems are complex systems, which include the physical and nonphysical artifacts, such as organization and management, manufacturing and component suppliers, utility/energy suppliers, financing/investment partners, research programs and legislation. As Hughes says: An artifact – either physical or nonphysical – functioning as a component in a system interacts with other artifacts, all of which contribute directly or through other components to the common system goal (1987, p.51).

Before it will be possible to start, CERN needs to solve the system's financing. CERN has made a unanimous decision to go ahead with the project. That allows CERN to start The FCC's design. This is a very costly project which goes way beyond the standard budget of CERN. It is possible that actors from outside Europe must step in, including United States, China, and Japan. This might transform fundamental organizational structure of CERN to a global organization, the European governance structure to global international governance and maybe even the European strategy for particle physics to global strategy.

Invention and development of the FCC is working with three scenarios: proton-proton, electron-positron and proton-electron collision. According to CERN, the scientists are conducting physics and detector studies for each option and see their feasibility. In parallel infrastructure, operation concepts and technologies required are analyzed (www.cern.ch). The problem here is that FCC

would be finished around year 2050. The technology of today will be very different to the technology of 2050 and many inventions, development and innovations will be necessary both during the building phase as well as once finished. The whole system is so complex and hence very vulnerable to the emergence of the reverse salient. Reverse salients according to Hughes are components in the system which are out of phase with the others. Such an immense system will take 30 years to build and will develop many reverse salients on the way (technological, infrastructural, organizational, financial, legal, etc). There are many examples which are now only to be imaginative, but to explain I will make up some. The geographical position is partially under the lac Lemman, which might emerge a problem of geographical placement even though a geographical and geological studies have been made. That might influence the position which must be changed - maybe moved or even be enlarged or it would have to go deeper under the surface and hence influencing the infrastructure, financial support, engineering, construction and further technological implications. And it is only the beginning.

The project has already critics within the physics community, where the cost of the building will possibly not have the scientific payback expected (www.nature.com). But what is the alternative if we do not start based on what we know now? There will be many problems to solve and the system will develop momentum (trajectory, the path in same direction excluding the alternatives) based on the choices taken today. But ultimately it will lead to new knowledge and its transfer to other industries which will hopefully maximize the socio-economic impact. The technological style will be influenced by many actors involved and maybe even a special 'CERN style' will be developed independent of national or geographical factors.

References:

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